

We very much appreciate the opportunity to comment on the National Open Research Forum (NORF) [Draft National Statement](#) on the Transition to an Open Research Environment.

We support that Preprints + Green routes will be allowed as part of the transition, even for hybrid (society) journals. Because of the vital role that quality society journals play in the advancement of science, we are happy to see that NORF does not ban hybrid journals (#s 3-5).

We support that Diamond OA models are encouraged (# 4). We are concerned that agnosticism on this point – as exhibited by Europe’s Plan S – will allow APC-based OA models to dominate the market, allowing public research funds to be diverted from learned societies that provide a valuable service to the scientific community to for-profit APC-based OA publishers. We do not see what problem that solves. Hence, in addition to encouraging Diamond OA models verbally, we would also like to see specific measures to stimulate Diamond OA over APC-based OA models.

We support that NORF allows for offsetting agreements between funders/libraries and publishers and the demand for transparency in such agreements (# 9). We hope that offsetting agreements will continue to play an important role in the transition to a fully open landscape. We hope this will be stimulated and considered as a desirable permanent OA solution (not just as a temporary solution in a transition period ‘that should be as short as possible’, as described in the preamble of Plan S).

The demand in # 7 that the license applied should fulfill the requirements of the Berlin Declaration (with a preference for CC BY) is consistent with Plan S. It ignores the fact that many researchers – especially in the arts and humanities, but including also some scientists – would sometimes prefer a more restrictive license for reuse. The application of a more restrictive license does not bar the rightsholder from granting permission for other uses in the future. It would also make some sense to mandate a CC BY or equivalent license, but to grant a no-questions-asked waiver upon request. This would allow the rightsholder to apply a more restrictive license only in cases in which she/he felt the necessity to do so.

Mandating CC BY or equivalent without such a waiver option treats all publications as if they were scientific articles. But published articles mean different things in different fields. In the sciences, for instance, it is more typical to perceive the publication as describing the experiment or reporting on the *results* of the research. Although priority in publication of results is vital, scientists fully expect others to build upon, modify, or abandon their results as science progresses. A CC BY or equivalent license makes some sense in the context of articles considered as containers for information to which the scientist is not wedded in a personal way. However, in the humanities, the publication itself actually *constitutes* the research. Translating a work of philosophy or poetry, for instance, into a foreign language is not something that can be done willy-nilly by an algorithm without destroying vital aspects of the work. An author or artist who has no objection to subjecting their work to that sort of treatment can always choose a CC BY or equivalent license. But *mandating* that all authors treat their works this way is unfair and fundamentally misunderstands the nature of research in the arts and humanities.

#s 14-18 of the Draft Statement about open data management are admirable. However, it may mean a lot of extra work for researchers. A shift of research money to data management would not be desirable. The same holds for #s 19-22 concerning the infrastructure for data management. Investments and salaries for support should come with extra money to support data management, and should not be cut out of regular research funds.

#s 26-27 of the Draft Statement about the academic career system and evaluation metrics are focused on creating a reward system for researchers to support Open Science. We are worried by the focus on

metrics here and hope that metrics will be used to inform, rather than to replace, peer review. We know of no metrics, for instance, that can fully capture the societal impacts of research. We also note that fundamental research is important, and has led to several discoveries of high importance for society in the long run (while not recognized as such on shorter terms). We would not support a policy that only rewards/values research that has immediate societal impact and diminishes the importance of fundamental research.

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